

COGNITIVE ACTIVITY MODEL OF THE LEARNING STATUS COMPONENT IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article considers learning as a system and emphasizes that its two main organizational components are learning and teaching, and interprets students' learning activities as activities aimed at achieving the goals of the learning process. It is acceptable to include cognitive needs, learning motives, learning objectives, tasks, and learning activities in the structure of training. It is accepted that knowledge and the process of learning this knowledge belong to the sources that create cognitive interests and needs.

Based on the analysis of the research materials obtained, the authors make the following generalization: regardless of the level of perception of the activity, the understanding of the goal always remains a necessary feature of it; In the absence of this sign, human activity, especially learning activity, cannot exist. It is also concluded that the functional structure of learning activities includes the following stages: 1) introductory-motivational stage; 2) operational-cognitive stage; 3) control-evaluation stage.

Keywords: Objective and subjective aspects of training activities; structure; mental activity; educational work; cognitive needs; cognitive interests; outward activity; internal activity; creative activity; teaching-problem situation.

Relevance of the research topic. The essence of the learning process can be interpreted according to the "teacher-learning material-learner" scheme, in other words, the process can be considered as a system that includes interconnected parts and has some properties that are not always in separate parts. When we move away from the nature of the elements of the system and focus on the relationship between them, we are confronted with the concept of the structure of the system. The dialectical unity of the structure with the elements is the main feature of the system. The essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, ie the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, the specificity of the relationship of the object to the situation. It is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary connections here without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction. It should not be forgotten here that There are also certain interdependencies between systems, including one another and dialectical connections. In the learning process, the teacher, the learner's activities and the learning material can be considered as "sub-systems" contained in this process. The solution to the everlasting problems of the learning process can be approached despite what we have said. Determining the structure (genetic and functional) of these "subsystems" leads to approaches to improving the management of the training system. However, no systematic research has been conducted in this area. Therefore, we claim the relevance of the topic of the article. learner activity and learning material can be viewed as "sub-systems" embedded in this process. The solution to the everlasting problems of the learning

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Interpretation of the research material obtained on the research topic. One of the scientific sources states: "Looking at the psychopedagogical pages of the past centuries, we see that in the history of world education, a rich experience has been accumulated at the root of the transfer of knowledge to the student. The ideas put forward and applied to implement the process of knowledge transfer to the student can be grouped into three groups: 1) Enlightening learning ideas; 2) Developmental learning ideas; 3) Educational training ideas." [2; 9]. Another pedagogical literature emphasizes: "Sometimes it is thought that learning is a simple process of imparting knowledge to students. In fact, it is the core of education. Training has complex

functions. There are two sides to the training as a teacher-student interaction: teaching and learning. The effectiveness of the training depends on the proper interaction of teachers and students in the teaching process, it depends to a large extent on the level of cognitive activity and interest of students in learning” [1; 210]. We can continue to think about training, because there are too many opinions about it in scientific sources. Based on the generalization of our research materials, we believe that training in educational institutions is a way of implementing education, which can be more accurately interpreted through the concept of “system”. In our opinion, in modern times, education should be understood as a system of education adequate to the emerging educational space in accordance with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution. The main components of this system are the educator and the learner. The learner is the pupil, the student, the follower, and others, in general, “someone who intends to assimilate the necessary part of human experience.”

Students' learning activities themselves are activities aimed at achieving the goals of the learning process. It has both objective and subjective aspects. If a student's activity is not aimed at fulfilling his / her responsibilities in the learning process, it cannot be considered a learning activity. Therefore, the objective aspect of the learning activity is related to the fact that it directs the student to the goals set for learning independently. The subjective aspect of the training activity is characterized and determined by the dominant motives of this activity. It is desirable that the dominant motives of the training activity are teaching-cognitive motives. The teacher's pedagogical influence should be directed to this situation. In this case, the objective and subjective aspects of the training activity overlap, and its activity has a public and personal meaning.

The activity of students in the learning process is complete, it is necessary to divide it into teaching-cognitive and control-assessment. This is important for a better analysis of training activities. Thus, as M.L.Fridman points out, any activity, including learning activities, consists of the following elements: need-motive-goal-task-work-operation. All this is done under certain internal and external conditions in relation to student activities. They should be included in the structure of activities. It shows that they must be distinguished both by the content of the motives and the specificity of the other elements. The model of training activity reflects its origin and development [12,178-179].

M.A. Hamzayev, who has a slightly different approach to the structure of training, shows that the following components can be included in the structure of training: cognitive needs, learning motives, learning goals, objectives, teaching activities. Educational work is different. This includes provocative (executive), program-purpose, active, control-regulatory (evaluative, checking, corrective) work [4; 131].

As can be seen, these two views on the structure of teaching complement each other. The facts obtained on the basis of psychological research allow us to

substantiate the well-known fact that the satisfaction of cognitive needs is a necessary condition for the normal development of a person, including his learning and learning activities. When learning begins with a person's cognitive needs, it becomes a key factor in ensuring his activity. Hence the cognitive interests, the main motives of learning. Based on this, N. Kazimov also notes that the knowledge covered by the subjects and the process of learning this knowledge belongs to the sources that create cognitive interests and needs [7; 108-111].

Cognitive interests in students have different stages of development, and it can manifest itself in different forms. This diversity is one of the reasons for the level of activity and independence of children in the learning process. The level of development of cognitive interests in students can be determined on three levels according to their content: simple, medium and high.

Formed cognitive interest not only increases the effectiveness of students' subsequent learning activities in training, but also scientifically based training, in turn, can improve students' cognitive interest. Innovation of knowledge, problem-solving, use of scientific and technical innovations, the importance of knowledge for the individual, for society, the involvement of children in creative activities, etc. are tools that help increase cognitive interest.

The need for cognition essentially expresses students' desire for knowledge. There is no doubt that this is due to cognitive interest. Man has a need to cope with the surrounding reality, not only in order to protect himself, but also for cognitive purposes.

A lot of research has been done on the cognitive needs and interests of schoolchildren. In general, over the past decade, educators and psychologists have studied the following cognitive needs and interests and identified the following:

1. The objective basis for the development of cognitive interest in students is the high level of teaching, its true scientific content, the pedagogically expedient organization of active and independent cognition.

2. Students' cognitive interests may have different levels of manifestation, stability and depth at different levels of development. The shapeless, broad, and basic interests of students provide a diverse basis for active and independent learning. Cognitive interest of students reflects the level of understanding of events, processes and patterns by students according to their content.

The highest level of development of cognitive interest is the level of creativity, which is due to the deep theoretical problems, the student's interest in performing the activity not in an easy way known to everyone, but in his own plan and method.

3. Under the influence of cognitive interest, activity becomes easier, freer and faster, which eliminates fatigue.

4. The stimulating effect of teaching on the formation of students' cognitive interest is very large. This influence stems from the content of the subject, activities, and the relationship between the participants in the learning process [5; 284-285].

Learning goals and objectives also have a special place and role in the structure of learning. It is this aspect that allows learning to be learning. In other words, learning becomes training when it takes a plan, a form that fulfills certain goals and objectives, and leads to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and habits. Training was possible where human activity was driven by conscious goals in order to acquire certain knowledge, habits and skills. The prerequisite for the formation of learning activities is the creation of conscious motives for the acquisition of certain knowledge, skills and habits in the subject.

Learning activities not only equip students with the knowledge, skills and habits necessary for various types of socially useful activities. At the same time, it develops in the student the ability to manage his mental processes, to select, organize and direct his work and operations, habits and experiences in relation to the problem to be solved.

Regardless of the level of perception of the activity, the understanding of the goal always remains a necessary feature of it. In the absence of this sign, there can be no human activity, especially learning activity [3; 230-238].

The system of actions that constitute work is ultimately managed and regulated for the purpose of that work. It is when the results of actions are evaluated from the point of view of purpose and they are corrected. The purpose of the work is to ensure that the properties and conditions of things are the basis for its implementation, control and correction.

The goal of the training activity is to present images in the brain as a dynamic model of the future outcome of the activity. The actual result of the work is compared with this desirable model of the future, it is he who manages and corrects the lines of action. Physiologists call this model of the work ahead and the results (goals program) that it predicts to the brain itself "work aspect" and "preventive reflection" (P.K.Anoxin), "action goal" and "required future model" (N.A.Bernstein), "essential importance" and "model of the future" (Mittelstedt, U. Ashby), "dynamic model" and so on they call. Although this difference stems from different assumptions about what the model consists of, how it is formed, and how it works, the idea of anticipating future work and reflecting their expected results in a certain way on the brain is a completely correct idea [6; 172].

Educational work, which allows to realize the goals and objectives of learning, also occupies one of the main places in its structure. Such work includes, first of all, executive work. A learner cannot acquire relevant knowledge, skills and habits without using those learning activities. Such work is work that directs a person to action. Program-specific work includes oral and written work, laboratory work, etc. related to meeting the requirements of the program. consists of. Active operational educational work is work aimed at activating the intellectual activity of students, creating cognitive activity in them. Such work stimulates the mental development of students, simply takes them away from reproduction.

N.Kazimov writes that the manifestations of student activity during training can be divided into three groups: external activity, internal activity and creative activity. Internal activity is more perfect than external activity and is more effective in learning. Students with internal activity succeed in learning [7; 108-111].

The highest form of activity is creative activity. It is typical for creative activity to find ways to solve a given task, to cope with it, and sometimes to identify original means. Creative activity plays an important role in the formation of the student's personality.

In learning, the student's cognitive activity is inseparable from independence. They complement each other. The student's independence in learning manifests itself in various forms: in the need for knowledge; being able to think independently; coping with a new situation; looking creatively to cope with a new task; striving to learn new knowledge radically; in a critical approach to the opinion of another in the matter being taught; being able to prove his point, etc. [3; 231].

Manifestations of student independence in the learning process can be observed when searching for information in sources, thinking about factual knowledge, strengthening skills, turning skills into habits, applying knowledge to practice, using knowledge in new situations.

The role of control-regulatory educational work included in the structure of training is also great. These works are mainly evaluative, verifying and corrective. With their help, it is possible to manage students' learning activities.

N.Kazimov distinguishes the following from the features that characterize the student's activity in training: the presence of cognitive operations in the learning process; manifestations of cognitive operations; the role of learning motives; cognitive interests in learning; communication in learning; activity and independence of students in learning. [7; 109]. In our opinion, N.Kazimov is right. In addition, it should be noted that during training, students not only acquire knowledge, but also get used to learning. A number of cognitive operations underlie learning and the ability to acquire knowledge. It is important to pay special attention not only to teaching skills, but also to cognitive operations.

Under the guidance of the teacher, the theory of the formation of cognitive operations in students' learning activities was developed by psychologists. According to the theory of mastering intellectual activity in stages (P.Y.Galper's concept), the analysis of activity comes to the fore in the training, and knowledge is considered as a derivative of activity and its mastering. Thus, according to P.Y.Galperin, training is a structure with the following components: a) the subject of change, the product (goal); b) the process of change, as well as reflection; c) knowledge of all the components of the activity mentioned.

In addition, P.Y.Galper showed that intellectual activity in mastering goes through the following six stages: 1) the stage of motivation; 2) FBA determination stage; 3) stage of material performance

of activity; 4) stage of performance of the activity in oral speech (speaking loudly); 5) the stage of performance of the activity with the help of internal speech (self-expression); 6) stage of performance of activity in mental form [10; 346].

In our opinion, it is necessary to add to Galperi's opinion that each cognitive operation can be approached as a system. Considering this point, N.Kazimov shows that the formation of any cognitive operation is a system in itself, as the student has to perform a number of alternating cognitive operations when performing the task, and in this sense, the student's learning activity is both content and also manifests itself as a system of cognitive operations aimed at the implementation of the educational task in terms of performance style. As with learning tasks, the cognitive operations that require them are varied [7; 110].

The positions of D.B.Elko and V.V.Davidov on the psychological structure of the training are also noteworthy. They highlight some features of the training activity and indicate its following components: 1) training conditions and tasks; 2) training work; 3) work on assessing the level of mastery [8; 326-334].

Learning conditions and tasks are characterized by the fact that students are instructed to master the general patterns of activity and the purpose of mastering them, as well as the examples and instructions necessary to find common ways to solve a particular type of problem. The training consists of students looking for or finding scientific concepts and general ways of doing things, as well as ways to remember them and apply them to the solution of characteristic problems. Supervision work is aimed at summarizing the results of their training based on a given example. Evaluation works record the final quality of mastering the given scientific knowledge and general ways of solving the problem.

One of the concepts related to the structure of the training is connected with the name of A.N.Leontyev. He distinguished the perception of a class of specific objects, their properties, as well as generalized cognitive processes. He showed that the first consists of knowledge, skills and habits and the possibility of mastering them in the process of learning. The latter are capable. Their acquisition occurs in the process of developing cognition [3; 230-238].

In general, the essence of these concepts is that in order to master the concepts, it is necessary to have the object, but also the attitude to it, communication, especially the activity of students with the object. In our opinion, the structural models of the training activities in question can be distinguished according to their formation and development and the functional connection of the individual elements. In this regard, Lingart's opinion is interesting. He writes: "We believe that the structure of learning has four interrelated components: motivation, cognition, execution and control. The first three are activities, control is related to the analysis of the activities carried out" [9; 571].

1. Introduction - motivation stage;
2. Operation - cognitive stage;
3. Control - evaluation stage;

It seems to us that a well-thought-out, effective, optimal learning activity in the study of any subject should include these stages.

The following training activities can be distinguished in the introductory-motivational phase:

1. Understanding the teaching-problem situation;
2. Defining key learning objectives;
3. Assessment of opportunities to study the training material.

In the operational-cognitive stage, students learn the content of the training material, acquire knowledge, skills and habits. In this case, the main training task is to determine the sequence of individual tasks and solve them.

At the control-assessment stage, students summarize what they have learned on the topic, include them in their general system of knowledge and skills, analyze their learning, determine whether they have completed the main cognitive task, what they have mastered, how they achieved their goals, and so on. considers issues, carries out necessary correction work.

Scientific novelty of research work. A model of activity (functional) has been identified as a key component of the student's learning system, which has a key role in both practical and theoretical terms in terms of defining and systematizing learning methods (binary in nature). The compatibility of the student's activity model with the teacher's activity model involves the combination of teaching and learning methods, which is related to the nature of the learning process.

Theoretical significance of the research. Determining the model of activity (functional) in which the student is the subject of the learning process has a positive impact on the development of the theory of improving the management of the system.

Practical significance of the research. Determining the student's model of activity (functional) as a tool in the learning process creates an adequate environment to eliminate errors that may be manifested in the solution of "didactic cognitive problems" in the direct (indirect, indirect) management of the system as a "stakeholder".

The result. 1) The student's model of activity (functional) in the learning process has both a practical and theoretical key role in terms of choosing and systematizing the forms of mental movement. 2) The operating models of the main components of the training system are compatible. This is due to the essence of the training process.

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HOW TO DEAL WITH PROFESSIONAL BURNOUT IN MEDICAL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Professional burnout of teachers is a very common and urgent problem of higher medical school. Mental health problems, manifestations of emotional burnout directly affect the health of teachers, their psycho-emotional state and professional qualities. The article provides a theoretical analysis of the causes, factors, forms and levels of professional burnout of teachers, outlines ways and means of diagnosis. The negative impact of burnout on the mental health of the individual, its formation and further professional development is substantiated and methods for preventing the development of this pathology are substantiated.

Key words: professional burnout, syndrome, education, mental health, stress, well-being.

The history of the term "emotional burnout" begins in the XVII century. when the Dutch surgeon Nicolaes Tulp said "shining on others, I burn myself", and in 1974 the American psychiatrist H. J. Freudenberger first drew attention to this phenomenon and described it as "defeat, exhaustion or wear and tear that occurs to humans due to sharply increased demands on own resources and forces ". The term "professional burnout" appeared in the psychology literature in 1974 to describe the mental state of healthy people who interact intensively with patients, clients and are constantly in an emotionally charged atmosphere during professional care. Currently, this term has the diagnostic status "Z 73.0 Burnout, state of life exhaustion" in the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision (ICD-10) -2015 -WHO Version for; 2015).

Occupational burnout is a condition of emotional, physical and mental exhaustion caused by chronic stress. This condition most often occurs among professionals who work in close contact with people and are forced to communicate a lot with others. This group includes teachers [1]. Given the current: drastic reform

changes in the structures of educational institutions, which are taking place against the background of the socio-economic crisis, associated not only with market relations in education, but also with the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic. Over the last two years, burnout has taken on a different form, with signs of isolation, fears for the lives and health of relatives, and distance learning. The transition to distance learning has created new challenges for teachers. We had to quickly master new forms and approaches to teaching. "Quarantine" factors influencing the development of burnout are divided into two groups: organizational and psychological - factors related to the new special organization of work in quarantine; psychological - factors associated with new psychological features of professional activity and their own subjective characteristics. Working in such a rhythm is extremely difficult to maintain your mental health and prevent emotional burnout.

There are the following main factors that play an important role in the formation of emotional burnout:

- ✓ personal - dissatisfaction with professional growth, lack of motivation at work, low wages;